

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B318
Date: 17 August 2007
Take Off 08:39:42Z
Landing: 14:04:29Z
Flight Time 5h24m47s

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden Baden

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stephen Mobbs	NCAS
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 2	Justin Peter	University of Leeds
9	Observer	Victoria Smith	University of Leeds
10	COPS	Volker Wulfmeyer	University of Hauenhof
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Flight Track:

B318 Track 17-AUG-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B318
 Date: 17 August 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Baden Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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080655		Start-Up	0.22 kft	160	48'46.91N, 8'05.33 E
083942		T/O	0.87 kft	216	Baden Baden
085027		Video	6.0 kft	095	Start FFC & UFC
085125	090455	Run 1.1	6.0 kft	180	C-B
090813	092144	Run 1.2	6.0 kft	014	B-C
092245	092604	Profile 1	6.0 - 2.6 kft	286	FL60 - 2.8k', QNH=1020mb
092604	093339	Run 2.1	2.7 kft	209	
092942		Event	2.6 kft	202	Ovhd R
093631	094401	Run 2.2	2.7 - 2.6 kft	003	2.8k' Rhine valley
094110		Event	2.6 kft	028	Overhead R
094457	095221	Profile 2	2.6 - 10.0 kft	116	From 2.8k', Interrupt at FL100
095406	095956	Profile 2	10.0 - 15.0 kft	269	
100939	101126	Run 3.1	9.0 kft	268	Near cloud tops
101433	101615	Run 3.2	9.0 kft	096	
101808	102143	Run 3.3	9.0 kft	283	
102202		Video	9.0 kft	261	Change tapes
102543	102749	Run 4.1	10.0 kft	111	
103101	103407	Run 5.1	10.5 - 10.6 kft	278	
103623	104522	Run 6.1	9.0 kft	168	
104552	105700	Run 7	9.5 kft	050	
105907	110317	Run 8	10.5 kft	020	
110626	111048	Run 9	11.0 kft	118	Cloud tops
111129	111930	Run 10	11.5 kft	266	Ice staying on cloud probes
112144	112534	Run 11	12.5 - 12.4 kft	012	500' below tops
112839	113405	Run 12	13.1 kft	144	
113406	113821	Profile 3	13.1 - 9.0 kft	250	
114006	114232	Run 13	9.0 kft	146	
114605	114856	Run 14	10.0 kft	321	
115225	115850	Run 15	12.0 kft	141	
115452		Video	12.0 kft	124	Change tapes
115850	120028	Profile 4	12.0 - 13.0 kft	001	
120342	120754	Profile 5	13.0 - 9.0 kft	218	
120951	121144	Profile 5	8.6 - 7.0 kft	193	st 120920
121815	123035	Run 16.1	7.0 kft	349	
123355	124929	Run 16.2	7.0 kft	213	
125315	130633	Run 17.1	8.5 kft	351	
130941	132500	Run 17.2	8.5 kft	205	
132518		Video	8.5 kft	167	Change tapes
133227	133423	Run 17.3	8.5 kft	012	Over Supersites
133405		Event	8.5 kft	014	Ovhd M
133939		Event	7.5 kft	291	Ovhd H
134127		Event	7.5 kft	280	Overhead R
134425	134914	Run 18	6.6 - 6.5 kft	132	
134521		Event	6.5 kft	106	Ovhd R
134651		Event	6.5 kft	107	Ovhd H
134906		Event	6.5 kft	122	Ovhd M
135213	135823	Run 19	5.4 - 5.3 kft	262	5.5k' on QNH1020
135355		Event	5.4 kft	288	Ovhd M
135629		Event	5.3 kft	295	Ovhd H
135820		Event	5.3 kft	297	Ovhd R
140429		Land	0.22 kft	075	Baden Baden
140858		Shutdown	0.22 kft	156	48'46.91N, 8'05.35E

B318 Track 17-AUG-07

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B318

Date: 17/08/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:19:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:51:26																Start Run 1.1 @ FL060	
08:52:00	200	0.07	2	5	1												
08:54:00	250	0.08		5	1												
08:56:00	260	0.08	83	3000	2000												
08:58:00	210	0.07	93	5	1												
09:00:00	140	0.07	233	5	5												
09:02:00	170	0.07	439	3	2												
09:04:00	190	0.07	535	10	10												
09:54:54																End Run 1.1	
09:08:13																Start Run 1.2 @ FL060	
09:09:00	200	0.08	584	10	1												
09:11:00	215	0.08	643	5	1												
09:13:00	150	0.07	939	5	1												
09:15:00	140	0.08	Fail	10	1												
09:17:00	220	0.10	253	2000	6000											B318A for FFSSP	
09:19:00	215	0.08	518	10	10												
09:21:00	185	0.07		5	1												
09:21:47																End of Run 1.2	
09:22:45	180	0.07		5	1											Start Profile 1 from FL060	
09:23:41	170	0.07		5	1											FL050	
09:24:37	120	0.07		5	1											FL040	
09:26:04																End of Profile 1 & Start Run 2.1 @ 2800'	
09:27:00	300	0.07	557	5	1												
09:29:00	465	0.07		5	1												
09:31:00	290	0.08	558	5	1												
09:33:00	375	0.08		10	1												
09:33:40																End of Run 2.1	
09:36:30																Start Run 2.2 @ 2800'	
09:37:00	300	0.07	5	10	1												
09:39:00	290	0.08	5	5	1												
09:41:00	200	0.07	560	15	2	2	800	160	1000						1		
09:43:00	440	0.08		10	1												
09:44:00																End of Run 2.2	
09:44:58	360	0.08	561	5	1											Start Profile 2 from 2800'	
09:46:15	310	0.07	581	5	1											FL040	
09:47:20	145	0.07	586	5	1											FL050	
09:48:23	160	0.08	630	2000	3000											FL060	
09:49:30	140	0.07	646	3												FL070	
09:50:43	150	0.07	899	4000	6000											FL080	
09:51:23	50	0.07		1												FL090	
09:52:21	180	0.10	1199	5000	5000											FL100	
09:55:15	120	0.12	2079	3000	1000											FL110	
09:56:22	5	0.06	2314													FL120	
09:57:44	4	0.07														FL130	
09:58:49	10	0.09														FL140	
09:59:56	20	0.09														End of Profile 2 @ FL150	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B318

Date: 17/08/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:19:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:09:41																Start Run 3.1 @ FL090	
10:10:00	65	0.08	2634	2	1												
10:11:29																End of Run 3.1	
10:14:33																Start Run 3.2 @ FL090	
10:15:00	75	0.07	2694	2	1												
10:16:17																End of Run 3.2	
10:18:08																Start Run 3.3 @ FL090	
10:19:00	100	0.07	2856	2	1												
10:21:43																End of Run 3.3	
10:25:43																Start Run 4.1 @ FL100	
10:26:00	55	0.08	3037	1													
10:27:49																End of Run 4.1	
10:30:58																Start Run 5.1 @ FL105	
10:31:00	40	0.08	3113	1	Noise												
10:33:00	55	0.07	3115														
10:34:07																End of Run 5.1	
10:36:22																Start Run 6 @ FL090	
10:37:00	100	0.07	3171	2	1												
10:39:00	110	0.07	3222	1000	1000												
10:41:00	95	0.08	3463	5	10												
10:43:00	95	0.07	3606	3	2												
10:45:00	240	0.11	4010	3000	9000												
10:45:22																End of Run 6	
10:45:52																Start Run 7 @ FL095	
10:46:00	170	0.14	4329	5000	8000												
10:48:00	60	0.07	4358	3	1												
10:50:00	100	0.08	4570	2	1												
10:52:00	155	0.12	4965	3000	5000												
10:54:00	110	0.07	5017	5	2												
10:56:00	55	0.08	5440	4000	4000												
10:57:01																End of Run 7	
10:59:07																Start Run 8 @ FL105	
11:00:00	110	0.09	5705	4000	4000												
11:02:00	90	0.09	5800	3	1												
11:03:16																End of Run 8	
11:06:26																Start Run 9 @ FL110	
11:07:00	40	0.08	5973	1													
11:09:00	70	0.07	6034	2													
11:10:48																End of Run 9	
11:11:31																Start Run 10 @ FL115	
11:12:00	80	0.10	6417	3000	3500	1											
11:14:00	350	0.17	7060	4000	4500	4	25								12		
11:16:00	7	0.14	7534	1000	2000	19	200								11		
11:18:00	3	0.07	7652	2	10												
11:19:34																End of Run 10	
11:21:43																Start Run 11 @ FL125	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B318

Date: 17/08/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:19:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:22:00	8	0.09	7978	1	Noise	100	25								12		
11:24:00	3	0.10	8163														
11:25:33																End of Run 11	
11:28:38																Start Run 12 @ FL130	
11:29:00	20	0.09	8393														
11:31:00	1	0.09	8509	1				Noise								Rearm 2 1	
11:33:00	70	0.08	8553	1000	1000			Noise									
11:34:04																End of Run 12 & Start Profile 3	
11:35:04	150	0.16	8813	2000	4500	30	200	Noise							5	FL120	
11:36:17	370	0.11	9180	900	3000	75	300	Noise							5	FL110	
11:37:20	65	0.08	9296	3												FL100	
11:38:21	500	0.10	9393	200	1000	50	800	1200	1000						8	End of Profile 3 @ FL090	
11:40:07																Start Run 13 @ FL090	
11:41:00	250	0.18	9724	1000	2000	110	800	2300	3000						8		
11:42:33																End of Run 13	
11:46:05																Start Run 14 @ FL100	
11:47:00	400	0.15	10166	1000	100	400	800	6700	4800						8		
11:48:54																End of Run 14	
11:52:26																Start Run 15 @ FL120	
11:53:00	35	0.08	10810	400	4000	300	400	21000	400						5		
11:55:00	2200	0.23	10994	4000	4000	700	700	70000	400						5		
11:57:00	560	0.17	11448	3000	3000	5		75									
11:58:50																End of Run 15 @ Start Profile 4 from FL120	
12:00:35	15	0.08														End of Profile 4 @ FL130	
12:03:48	4	0.08														Start Profile 5 from FL130	
12:04:40	50	0.22	11520	2000	2000	190	800									FL120	
12:05:46	130	0.19	11718	2000	2000	200	800									FL110	
12:06:58	45	0.09	11811	900	100	95	750	1200	4000						3	FL100	
12:07:52	160	0.15	11812	900	100	110	700	15000	5000						3	FL090	
12:10:22	120	0.08	12075	1500	100											FL080	
12:11:28	270	0.07	12167	1500	10	1		190								End of Profile 5 @ FL070	
12:18:12																Start Run 16.1 @ FL070	
12:19:00	110	0.07	12187	5	1												
12:21:00	220	0.07		5	1												
12:23:00	320	0.07	12188	10													
12:25:00	160	0.10	12106	110	60	65	700	2000	1000						1		
12:27:00	130	0.07	12211	20	10	12	800	800	6000						3		
12:29:00	190	0.08	12218	100	20	25	550	1900	4000						1		
12:30:35																End of Run 16.1	
12:33:56																Start Run 16.2	
12:34:00	170	0.08	12226	10	1												
12:36:00	200	0.10	12229	100	20	15	775	1800	6000						1		
12:38:00	120	0.12	12263	200	100	3	500	900	4000						8		
12:40:00	150	0.07	12296	200	100												
12:42:00	170	0.08		10	1												
12:44:00	210	0.07		10	1												

CVI log B318

8/17/07 7:26:33 AM PRESSURE HIEGHT 230
8/17/07 8:51:01 AM Start Run 1.1 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:04:30 AM End Run 1.1 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:07:48 AM Start Run 1.2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:21:20 AM End Run 1.2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:22:20 AM Start Profile 1 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:25:47 AM End Profile 1 Start run 2.1(AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:33:13 AM End run 2.1(AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:36:07 AM start run 2.2(AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:43:35 AM end run 2.2(AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:44:32 AM start profile 2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:51:56 AM interrupt profile 2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:53:40 AM restart profile 2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 9:59:30 AM end profile 2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 10:06:58 AM switched to (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:09:14 AM start run 3 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:11:02 AM end run 3 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:14:08 AM start run 4 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:14:22 AM start run 3.2 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:15:52 AM end run 3.2 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:17:43 AM start run 3.3 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:21:18 AM end run 3.3 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:25:18 AM start run 4.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:27:24 AM end run 4.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:30:33 AM start run 5.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:33:42 AM end run 5.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:35:57 AM start run 6.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:44:56 AM end run 6.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:45:27 AM start run 7.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:56:35 AM end run 7.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 10:58:43 AM start run 8.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:02:51 AM end run 8.1 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:06:01 AM start run 9 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:10:23 AM end run 9 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:11:05 AM start run 10 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:19:05 AM end run 10 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:21:19 AM start run 11 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:25:09 AM end run 11 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:28:14 AM start run 12 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:33:48 AM end run 12 start profile 3(CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:37:56 AM end profile 3 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:39:41 AM start run 13 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:42:05 AM end run 13 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:45:40 AM start run 14 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:48:29 AM end run 14 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:51:59 AM start run 15 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 11:58:33 AM end run 15 start profile 4 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 12:00:09 PM end profile 4 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 12:03:17 PM start profile 5 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 12:07:37 PM interrupt profile 5 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 12:18:11 PM restarting profile 5 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 12:18:33 PM start run 16 (CVI MODE)
8/17/07 12:26:04 PM CHANGED TO AEROSOL MODE (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 12:30:10 PM END RUN 16.1 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 12:33:35 PM START RUN 16.2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 12:49:08 PM END RUN 16.2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 12:52:48 PM START RUN 17.1 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 1:06:03 PM END RUN 17.1 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 1:09:16 PM START RUN 17.2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 1:24:35 PM END RUN 17.2 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 1:33:41 PM START RUN 17.3 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 1:41:23 PM END RUN 17.3 (AEROSOL MODE)
8/17/07 1:42:26 PM START OF RUNS OVER SUPER SITES AT 6500 AND 5500 AND THEN LAND
(AEROSOL MODE)

Flight:

B318

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezvorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 17/09/2007
16:01:04**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

17/09/2007 15:52:45

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B318

Date: 17/08/2007

Instruments

1. TWC – status light flashing at 1115Z, FL115, -7C outside, Status word 4091, Para 72 TSAM out of limits (640) , TSAM reading 635 DRS units. Also, Para 75 EVAP 1 below limit (2110), reading 2095 DRSU. Happened occasionally during rest of high level work.
2. FFC – picture very hazy on ground, other 3 clear. Possibly dirty window.
3. GIN – switched on after t/o (Operator error)
4. FFC – froze over at 0955, -6. Heater switched on since t/o. Cleared on descent. Froze again around 1100Z, FL115
5. Turb Probe – some freezing at 1009Z, AOA Differential affected. All channels affected when descending out of icing at 1155Z
6. Satcom C – occasional messages “satcom hardware status not available” at menu option 5.
7. JW – became noisy out of cloud from 1115Z after going through moderate icing. Okay after 1130Z
8. De-Iced Temp – reading 0 DRSU (-103deg C), from 1155 to 1208Z then okay.
9. Nevzorov – TWC alarm on at 1156Z, possible vane failure. Switch TWC Control Unit off.

Note: Nevz TWC = 90 deg C, LWC = 70 deg C (for all flights from B310)

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

2 rcvd from FAAM

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B318:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Brief	No brief is available so far for this flight. It will be almost identical to all other COPS flights.
De-brief	Stephen Mobbs is typing this up.
Mission Scientist's log	Stephen Mobbs is typing this up.
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Camera

4 x Upward Facing Camera

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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